

Principles, Pattern, Functions and Interactions of Bios

Introduction

The purpose of this attempt was to review a comprehensive and fundamental explanation of life. In his book *What is Life?* Erwin Schrödinger replied with his own concept of "negentropy (i.e. negative entropy)". The question still remains unanswered however. This study is an attempt for indicate the nature of life. To discover hear a general basic theory of life is novel.

partial [partially, half (semi)] open systems:

Figure 1. E, matter, S balance for a stationary open system with chemical reactions (linear stationary processes: principle of minimum entropy production by Prigogine)

[partial open system: e.g.: molecules, filters, membranes ~ skin ~ bone ~ tissue ~ organs ~ organism ~ brain: bloody barrier ~ memory]

↓ ~

Information (I) principle: max./min. = stationary (opt. = 1):

↓ ~

Figure 2. efficiency: min. input → max. I/min. entropy production = stationary (opt. = 1) → effectivity (exergetic utilization rate) (→optimal efficiency: input optimum → I (ΔI) optimum → effectivity optimum)

Materials and methods

Data of this exploration show that nature of life is predictable by suitable methods for measurement like e.g. spectroscopy, microscopy, crystallography, non linear partial differential stochastic equations and stochastic.

Following figures are examples of the study.

Figure 3. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Symmetry/Asymmetry interaction.

Figure 4. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Order/Free Energy interaction.

Results

Life in general is characterized mainly by increasing complexity.
 A fundamental building block of the genesis of the process, to and decay of structures of a system (state change) its structural development.
 In other words, the dynamics of interaction relations between stability and flexibility created the degree of complexity of a system in form of modeling as for example morphogenesis respectively pattern development.
 A possible measure of this amount of structural change is in analogy the relationship of symmetry and asymmetry.

e.g.:

Nature (e.g.: Ist/Soll)
 $x \sim \text{Input} \sim \text{environment}$
 $(\sim y/x)$

Life (e.g.: Ist ~ Soll)
 $z \sim \text{life box} \sim \text{system}$
interactio(ns): $y/x = z \leftrightarrow z = y/x$

Culture (e.g.: Soll/Ist)
 $y \sim \text{Output} \sim \text{environment}$
 $(\sim y/x)$

action: $e \rightarrow \text{actio}$ $e \leftrightarrow s$ **reactio**^(a)
 $-kT \ln Z \sim N e^{-V(\xi)/T} \sim \varphi$

interaction(s): $s \leftrightarrow s$
 $S/-S = \xi \sim \ln Z$ ($Z = e^{-F/kT}$)
stationary principle of entropy production
 e.g.: evolution eq. \sim order parameter ξ
 (stationary irreversible processes: evolut. eq.)
 [stationary principle of entropy production:
 optimum: minimax = maximin = 0]

$s \leftrightarrow e \rightarrow \text{reaction: } e$
 $F \sim f(\xi) \sim V(\varphi)$
 [E_{fl} ~ probability density]

action: \rightarrow ^(b)
 Hamilton: principle of: least action
 \sim statistical physics: basic model:
 $F = E - ST = \mu N$

interaction(s):
 \sim stationary interact. \leftrightarrow interaction principle
 $F = U - TS \sim \Omega := -kT \ln Z$
 (Helmholtz \sim statistical pot.)
 $\sim V(\varphi) = \varphi$
 (Higgs mechanism:
 E_{Min} = spontaneous symm. breaking)
 $\sim f(\xi) = N/e^{V(\xi)/T}$
 (probability density)
 $\sim F = -kT \ln Z$
 (statistical thermodyn.: basic formula)
 \sim Landau theory of phase transitions:
order parameter η
 \sim generalized: Ginzburg-Landau-theory:
 order parameter fct. $\eta(r)$, functional
 $\{\eta(r)\}$
 $\sim \Omega = F - \mu N$
 (\sim thermodyn. pot.)
 [μN = chemical pot. · mean particle]

\rightarrow **reaction:**
 \sim least reaction
 $E = F + ST = \mu N - T^2(\Omega/T)_T$

↕ ~

e.g.:

~ **symm./asymm. = partial symm.** ~ **stability/flexibility = partial stability** ~ **growth/decay = development** ~ **selection/variation = mutation**
 ~ **differential eq.: quality: life: arise/pass = development** ~ **reaction/action = interaction** ~ **Hamilton's principle** ~ **logistic function** ~ **order parameter**
 ~ **evolution eq. ~ deterministic/stochastic = deterministic chaos** ~ **evolution: necessity (~ law)/chance = develop**
 ~ **invariant/variant = partial invariant (~ e.g.: covariance)** [~ e.g.: universal scaling] {~ dimensionless quantities: e.g.: order parameter, partition function}

↕ ~ principles of life:

e.g.:

m-E equivalence

~ **I: conversion: physics ~ mathematics: m-factor-E**
 ~ **life: principle: principle of: opt. use/least friction = stationary action** {~ e.g.: $E\eta [= \hat{H}\eta(J)]$ }
 {irreversible Schrödinger eq. [Hamilton ~ Schrödinger ~ de Broglie]
 analogy: Classic/QM = Thermodyn.
 ~ function: Lagrange L ~ Hamilton H /(operator: Hamilton $\hat{H} =$ Schrödinger E) = Schrödinger $\hat{E}\xi$ ~ evolution eq. $\mathcal{L}\xi$
 [~ Schrödinger eq.: reversible (time-dependent, time-independent, nonlinear)/irreversible $\hat{E}\xi =$ stationary ~ nonlinear $\hat{E}\xi$]
 ~ $L = H/(\hat{E} = E\xi) = \hat{E}\xi \sim \mathcal{L}\xi$ [general: $\hat{\mathcal{L}}\xi = S\xi \sim$ Riemann fct. $\xi(s)$]}

~ **E: bound/free = internal**
 ~ **life: interaction: constant/E = term**
 ~ **meta/trans = syn**
 ~ **m/E = I ~ interaction: force/exchange = exchange principle**
 ~ **interaction exchange: m/E = I (e.g.: quant ~ fundamental)**

↕ ~

Figure 5. System-environment-interaction relation

The more complex the more important corresponding fairness is sustainable life in principle

Figure 6. Logistic growth of a partial open system by energy of friction/kinetic friction interaction.

Figure 7. Logistic growth of partial open systems by e.g. mutualism/parasitism interactions.

Figure 8. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Selection/Variation interaction.

Figure 9. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Action/Use interaction.

Figure 10. Cybernetics: natural control circuit

Conclusion

As a consequence of my findings, I recommend that presumption:

Evolution = Increase (degree of) complexity and raised so the number of the degrees of: invariant freedom/variant bond = interaction for a s

~ Life = Living s can be self regulated change his number of the degrees of: invariant freedom/variant bond = interaction.

~ Natural synthesis = Living s can be self regulated raised his number of the degrees of: invariant freedom/variant bond = interaction.

Consequence: The more complex the more degrees of: invariant freedom/variant bond = interaction.

Apparently follow life approximately the optimal friction for efficiency energy use.

In short:

Life = Δ ~ amount of complexity level structure: emergence/decay = Δ (production, transformation, ...) [development ~ genesis]

{development: preservation/decay = change (Δ)}

~ symmetry/asymmetry = approx. symmetry (stationary: opt.: \approx partially symmetrical)

Based on the above criteria, we can identify appropriate size relationships in the evolution (origin)
as suitable indicators for the essential characteristics of life.

Evolution go step by step a nature way of life ($\sim \Omega \leq 1$) as a complementary interaction process with each other between symm. and asymm.

by symmetry-breakup: physical \Rightarrow chemical (prebiot.) + prebiol. \Rightarrow biological [reverse evolution: $\Omega \rightarrow 0$ or > 1]

Example: nucleons \Rightarrow crystallization, (quantum) crystals, crystalloide, crystalline proteins, protein crystals,
(bio) molecules (monomere: nucleotide...), biocrystals, carbon, virus (Mimiviridae, Mamaviridae, Sputnik) \Rightarrow protobionts (eobionts),
prokaryots (archaeas + bacteria), eukaryots [algae, corals, plankton), sponges (glassy sponge...)]

~ natural genesis: physico (cosmochemistry) \Rightarrow chemo (stereochemical) + abiot. (abiogen) \Rightarrow bio.

Example: elements \Rightarrow nucleotide, biomats \Rightarrow photo, (bio) macromolecules [(bio)polymere]
(rna, dna, haemoglobin, little proteins, amino acids, carbon,...).

**The more complex the more significant corresponding synergies is sustainable life in principle
(survival rate rise by increasing lability as a result of growing interactions
and the associated increased need of regulation)**

Figure 11. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Cooperation/Complementary interaction.

Figure 12. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Coevolution/Evolution interaction.

**The more complex the more corresponding destructive is temporary life in principle
(survival rate rise by increasing liability as a result of growing interactions
and the associated increased need of regulation)**

Figure 13. Logistic growth of a partial open system by e.g. Mutualism/Predation interaction.

Figure 14. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Maximin/Minimax interaction.

Figure 15. Logistic growth of a partial open system by selfless/self-preservation interaction.

The more complex structures the more simplifying corresponding essential relations is well-syn life in principle

Figure 16. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Structures/Amorphous interactions.

Figure 17. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Character/Genesis interactions.

Figure 18. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Order/Order/Order/Disorder interactions.

Figure 19. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Order/Chaos interactions.

The more complex structures the more simplifying corresponding essential relations is syngenes life in principle

Figure 20. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Efficiency/Sustainability interactions.

Figure 21. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Culture/Nature interactions.

Figure 22. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Cultural Values/Natural Values interactions.

Figure 23. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Cultural/Natural interactions.

The more complex structures the more simplifying corresponding essential relations is syndevelop life in principle

Figure 24. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Order/Asymm. interactions.

Figure 25. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Stability/Adaptation interactions.

Figure 26. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Structure formation/Structure development interactions.

Figure 27. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Degrees of Freedom/Bonding interactions.

Principles of Life

Figure 28. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Order/Syntropy synergy.

Figure 29. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Syntropy/Synfo. synergies.

Figure 30. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Order parameter/Genesis synergy.

Figure 31. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Syntropy/Synfo. synergies.

Genesis of less to much more complex life

Figure 32. Logistic growth of a partial open system in a unit circle by coordination Order parameter/Partition function synergies.

Fundamental Principle of Life

Partial order of a partial open system

Figure 34. Nature of Principles

Canonic Map

Partial order of a partial open system

Figure 35. Nature of Life Genesis

Figure 36. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Culture/Nature synergies.

Figure 37. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Formation/Info. synergies.

Figure 38. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Purpose/Medium synergy.

Figure 39. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Culture/Nature synergies.

Figure 40. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Culture/Nature wellsyn.

Figure 41. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination k-/–k- Universe synergies.

Life Genesis by Horizontal, Vertical and Diagonal Symmetry breaking

Figure 42. Logistic growth of a partial open system by Symmetry/Asymmetry interaction.

Riemann surface

Figure 43. Symmetry breaking by Life Genesis.

Figure 44. Dimensions of bios Genesis.

Figure 45. pān of kósmo Genesis.

Transformations: e.g.: Dimensionless Entities:

Figure 46. ∞-Dimension of Life Genesis.

Figure 47. ∞-Dimension of Life Genesis by Complex Sphere.

Figure 48. Many-Valued by ∞-Dimensions of Life Genesis.

Figure 49. Non-Dimensions of Life Genesis by Unit Sphere.

Figure 50. Logistic growth of a partial open system by coordination Friction/Motion synergy.

Transformations of dynamical Systems

Scale invariance analogy ~ emergence ~ symmetry breaking ~ bifurcation (~ Verzweigung) ~ compactification ~ universal order parameter [e.g.: self-similarity, evolution equations (Hamilton's principle and eq., nonlinear stochastic DE ~ Schrödinger eq.), isomorph ~ homoeomorph (structure equality: algebraic ~ topological)]	Nonlinear Complex System	Elements	Order Parameter	Pattern Formation
Macro	universe ecological societies economical	matter, E, I culture, life, nature individuals, institut., etc. economic agents	density and temperature ecological conditions and behaviour social conditions and behaviour economic conditions and behaviour	cosmogenesis ecologic develop social develop economic develop
Meso	populations physio psyche brain organism fluids genetic	creatures neural networks mind neurons cells molecules molecules	density psychosomatic cell assembly of nerve impulses synapses concentrations temperature- and density gradient genom	morphogenesis psychosomagenesis psychogenesis neuralgenesis biogenesis chemosynthesis gensynthesis
Micro	atom quantum field field	nucleons particles waves radiation	bond number density and temperature pressure density	element synthesis nucleogenesis waves motion radiation spectrum

Figure 51. Structure formation of Life

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